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THE MATHEMATICAL APPARATUS FOR CALCULATING THE SCATTERING COEFFICIENT OF A CYLINDRICAL PERMANENT MAGNET MAGNETIZED ALONG THE LENGTH

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Annotation: The paper presents the mathematical apparatus for the analytical calculation of the magnetic inductions of working points and the scattering coefficient of a cylindrical permanent magnet magnetized along its length. The concept "working points of the permanent magnet" and the new expressions of the shape permeability coefficient and the magnetic conductivity of the scattering induction of a cylindrical permanent magnet magnetized along the length are imported. The data and analysis of the calculations and the experimental research are presented.

Keywords: permanent magnet, working point, induction, scattering coefficient

Introduction. In recent decades, powerful permanent magnets (PM), in particular NdFeB (neodymium-iron-boron), SmCo (samarium-cobalt), have been widely used in various apparatuses and devices, as a result of which new ones are being created and the existing ones are being improved.

As a result, the simplification and the improvement of the accuracy of the mathematical apparatus for calculating the main magnetic parameters of PM become priority research problems.

In the calculation and design processes of any device with a PM, it is necessary to calculate the parameters of the working point of the PM (neutral OO cross-section of the PM, Fig. 1), in particular, the magnetic induction B_0 and the magnetic field strength H_0 .

Figure 1 – Polarization and dimension assignments of the PM

1. The magnetic field created by the PM in space depends not only on the values of the magnetic induction B_0 in the neutral OO cross-section of the PM, but also on the values of the magnetic induction of the N or S poles, respectively B_N or B_S ($B_N = B_S$).

Therefore, it is proposed to import the concept of "working points" of the PM, taking into consideration not only the value of the magnetic induction in the neutral cross-section; but also at the poles.

2. The study, analysis, and comparison of the scientific and technical literature on the calculation of magnetic parameters of PM indicate a presence of contradictions in the expression of the definition of the PM's convexity coefficient, which causes a sharp difference in the calculated and experimental results. In particular, the expression of the convexity coefficient given on page 459 of the source [1-7].

3. The graphoanalytical method given in the source [1] for determining the magnetic scattering fluxes of PM, consequently also the working flow at the PM poles, is extensive and labor-intensive.

4. According to the source [3], determining the value of the permeability coefficient of the PM shape, where PM is considered as a rotating ellipsoid, is labor-intensive, and the simplified formula given in the source [2], in some cases gives a notable error deviation.

Proposed tasks.

1. To develop a mathematical apparatus using which the values of magnetic induction at the working points and the scattering coefficient of the PM magnetized along the length can be calculated analytically.

2. To prove the expediency of using the mathematical apparatus by practical calculation.

Problem solving.

The development of the mathematical apparatus for calculation is carried out with the help of literature [1-7].

The following permissions are made:

– the material of the PM is homogeneous, the PM is magnetized in a homogeneous magnetic field with the corresponding axis until saturation, and stabilization is done.

1. In the mathematical apparatus, the following parameters are the initial data

- the brand of the PM;
- the length of the PM, ℓ_{PM} , mm;
- the diameter of the PM, d_{PM} , mm (Fig. 1).

2. Referencing the directory, the following parameters of the PM’s material are registered:

- the coercive force by induction, H_{cB} , A/m;
- the residual induction, B_r , T;
- the maximum energy product, $(BH)_m$, J/m³.

3. The convexity coefficient of PM’s material is determined

$$\vartheta_c = 2 \sqrt{\frac{H_{cB} B_r}{(BH)_m} - \frac{H_{cB} B_r}{(BH)_m}}$$

4. The value of the permeability coefficient m_a of the PM form is determined.

For a cylindrical PM with a $\frac{d_{PM}}{\ell_{PM}}$ ratio of the 0,1÷10 interval (except when $\frac{d_{PM}}{\ell_{PM}} = 1$), it is suggested to use the following expression

$$m_p = 2,46 \left(\frac{d_{PM}}{\ell_{PM}} \right)^{-1,32}$$

when $\frac{d_{PM}}{\ell_{PM}} = 1$, $m_p = 3$.

5. The parameters of the PM are determined in the OO neutral cross-section (Fig. 1, 2).

$$B_0 = \frac{a - \sqrt{a^2 - 4\mu_0 \vartheta_c m_p H_{cB} B_r}}{2\vartheta_c}, H_0 = \frac{B_0}{\mu_0 m_p},$$

where $a = (B_r + \mu_0 m_p H_{cB})$, $\mu_0 = 4\pi 10^{-7} Hn/m$.

Figure 2 – The magnetic field of the PM and the magnetic inductions at the sections

6. The magnetic conductivity of PM is determined

$$\Lambda_{PM} = \frac{B_0 S_{PM}}{H_0 \ell_{PM}},$$

where S_{PM} is the area of PM's transverse cross-section $S_{PM} = \pi d_{PM}^2/4$.

7. To determine the magnetic conductivity of the scattering induction (fluxes), the following expression is suggested

$$\Lambda_\sigma \Lambda_\sigma = \mu_0 (1,48d_{PM} + 0,91\ell_{PM}).$$

8. The total magnetic conductivity is determined

$$\Lambda_{PM\Sigma} = \frac{\Lambda_{PM0}\Lambda_\sigma}{\Lambda_{PM0} + \Lambda_\sigma}.$$

9. The magnetic induction of scattering is determined

$$B_\sigma = \frac{\ell_{PM}}{S_{PM}} \Lambda_{PM\Sigma} H_0.$$

10. Magnetic induction at the PM pole is determined (Fig. 2).

11. Magnetic induction at the PM pole is determined (Fig. 2)

$$B_N = B_0 - B_\sigma.$$

12. The scattering coefficient by magnetic induction is determined

$$k_\sigma = \frac{B_0}{B_\sigma}.$$

13. The B(H) characteristics of the PM is built on the coordinate axis plane according to the following expression (Fig. 3)

$$B_i = B_r \frac{H_{CB} - H_i}{H_{CB} - g_c H_i},$$

where the values of H_i are picked from the range 0 to H_{CB} .

Figure 3 shows the characteristic of the PM and the locations of A_0 and A_N working points.

Figure 3 – B(-H) characteristic and working points of the PM

Research results.

A cylindrical PM of the brand N52 was selected for the study, with the following parameters: ℓ PM=30mm, dPM=50mm.

Step one. The reference source provides the following parameters: $H_{CB}=796 \cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_r=(1,43 \div 1,48)T$, $(BH)_m=(398 \div 422) \cdot 10^3 J/m^3$:

The following parameters are selected for the calculation: $H_{CB}=796 \cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_r=1,43T$, $(BH)_m=398 \cdot 10^3 J/m^3$.

According to the presented mathematical apparatus for calculation, the following results were obtained: $B_0=0,7905T$, $H_0=499,5 \cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_\sigma=0,3899T$, $B_N=0,4006T$, $k_\sigma = 1.97$:

Step two.

The PM parameters according to B_N were experimentally investigated using a teslameter and a webermeter.

The magnetic flux at the pole N of the PM was measured using an induction winding with 1 spire.

The magnetic flux was measured using a microwebermeter $\Phi 5050$.

After averaging several measurements and calculating them by magnetic induction, the following result was obtained: $B_N=0,4308T$.

At the PM pole, the magnetic induction was measured using a BST-600 teslameter.

The averaged value of the magnetic induction measured at different points of the PM pole was $B_N=0,4315T$.

The relative error of the experimental research was about 0,2 %.

The relative error of the calculation and the experimental calculations of the B_N induction at the PM pole N was about 8 %.

Concluouon.

1. The introduction to the concept of "working points" into the theory of the PM represents the parameters of the PM more profoundly.

2. The expressions of determining the shape permeability coefficient and the magnetic conductivity of the scattering induction of a cylindrical PM magnetized along the length accurately represent the real values and are applicable in the calculation process.

3. The developed mathematical apparatus is sufficiently accurate to provide an analytical calculation of the parameters of the PM. It is applicable in educational, engineering, and scientific research in the calculation and design processes of apparatus and devices with a PM.

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